

PROMOTING ACADEMIC HEALTH USING WELLNESS AND YOUTHFULNESS (PAHUWAY) FOR SECONDARY SCHOOL HEADS OF SULTAN KUDARAT

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the stress management practices and determined the challenges of the secondary school heads in the Division of Sultan Kudarat. The study employed the mixed methods research design wherein the survey and individual interviews were conducted. The survey checklist was adapted and administered to 27 randomly selected schools. Findings showed that the secondary school heads in the Division of Sultan Kudarat prefer to plan the job they want to perform ahead of time to manage time better in situations where they feel stressed as *A/ways*. They encountered challenges in managing workplace stressors: multi-tasking, the issue of power playing for new items, and the percentages on projects. A seminar/workshop will be done to bring solutions to these challenges.

Keywords: *Academic Health, Wellness, Youthfulness, Secondary School Heads, Sultan Kudarat, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

By incorporating the Ilonggo term "PAHUWAY," which means "rest," the title implies that the research will explore ways for school leaders to find balance, rejuvenation, and stress relief in their high-pressure positions.

This study aims to promote the overall well-being and stress management strategies for school leaders, including both heads and administrators. The focus is on using

wellness practices and maintaining a youthful mindset to cope with the demands of their roles.

Stress management in a worldwide setting picture out an organization as to how resources flow within the practice of supervision. It creates a culture of productivity, positivity, and upgrading of skills among members once it is well handled. Strategies are identified and applied by leaders and managers in all workplace which psychologically, emotionally, and physically affects every employee regardless of position if stress is not properly controlled. If not given attention, it changes behavior, perceptions, and practices among employees, which affects the performance and hampers the production as desired by every organization.

School heads' management of stress varies from one's creativity and efficiency. School leaders are challenged to think about what is best for the teachers, learners, and other employees and apply interventions creating an environment that change the effect on the workers. School heads' positivity brings good results in withstanding any challenges amid adversities. Aomo & Ogolla (2018), concluded that secondary school directors with a high sense of self-efficacy have better ways to handle challenging conditions than those with poor self-efficacy. Principals with high efficiency may handle stress better than leaders with principals who have low-esteem. This was because extremely self-efficient secondary school directors were able to handle any stressful situation. While Suleman et al. (2018), revealed that leaders with problems could produce numerous disagreeable and unpleasant results for the organization and its workforce, which pessimistically and undesirably affect the organization's overall performance. Accordingly, until stress is treated, various feelings of discomfort, struggles, challenges, and disease will take place. Stress is inevitable. Sahoo (2016) posits that where stress is not identified and addressed promptly, it will have an effect on organization and community soon. The organizational effects of stress can have a significant negative impact on the organization, in a wide range of areas such as: high personnel turnovers and recruitment costs, high levels of absenteeism and presenteeism, lower productivity levels such as stress exposure, increased health and safety issues, litigation organizations, reputational damage and increased training costs.

A rejoinder by Hartney (2020) that if stress is properly bring various diseases as a cause or precipitating factor, ranging from general health concerns such as cold and wound healing to life-threatening conditions such as coronary heart disease and cancer. Exposure to stress is indicated in most physical and mental conditions in the longer term. The impact of stress is generally negative it leads to problems such as unsatisfactory results, family issues, poor social relationships, health concerns, and unproductive organization. While the effects of stress are different depending on the situations and characteristics of the individuals concerned, the outcomes for the individuals are generally unpredictable. Depression, anxiety, downheartedness, stress, and deceit may be described as outcomes. Stress has disadvantageous effects on employees' productivity, (Benoliel & Barth, 2017).

Stress management practices used by the school head greatly affect the educational system, which introduces either positive or negative change in culture. Failure

to solve stress within the system will surely cause low productivity and less effective strategies, less participation, and lack of engagement during meetings and on coping with standards for school performance. Each school is an independent entity and has its own peculiarity, that this particular organizational culture had existed in the past before the school head came (Cabigao 2019). Organizational culture generally involves the belief that staff can learn what to do and what not to do, including practices, values, and assumptions about their job, in which the organization's core values begin with its leadership, which then translates into a leadership style. Which means that organizational culture was part of the school community, even from time immemorial, of what their previous school leaders and colleagues had learned. The school group has its definition of what's or isn't successful with this concept (Tsai 2019).

The various stress management practices that school heads need to adapt and apply to suppress stress to come up with a productive institution. It is, therefore, the intent of this study to cascade options that best suited for the school heads' physical, mental, emotional, and psychological stresses.

Research Question

Specifically, this research aimed to answer the following question:

What is the level of stress management practices of Secondary school heads, in terms of:

- a. Proactive Stress Management;
- b. Avoidance and Solitude, and
Distraction and Social Interaction?

METHODOLOGY

The study employs a quantitative approach to investigate the stress management practices of public secondary school heads. A survey is administered to a sample of school heads to gather numerical data on their stress management strategies, coping mechanisms, and perceived stress levels. The survey includes standardized scales and questionnaires to quantify the variables of interest. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistical tests are used to analyze the data, and the results are presented in the form of means, standard deviations, and correlations. It was conducted among twenty-seven (27) secondary school heads in the Division of Sultan Kudarat for the school year 2023-2024.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

On the level of stress management practices of secondary school heads in terms of proactive stress management was revealed as "Often", in terms of Avoidance and Solitude it was found out as "sometimes, and in terms of Distraction and Social Interaction it was revealed as 'Seldom'".

On the level of Stress Management Practices of Secondary School Heads in terms of Proactive Stress Management

Stress management practices used by the school head greatly affect the educational system, which introduces either positive or negative change in culture. Failure to solve stress within the system will surely cause low productivity and less effective strategies, less participation, and lack of engagement during meetings and on coping with standards for school performance.

Table 1. Stress Management Practices of Secondary School Heads in terms of Proactive Stress Management

As a secondary school administrator, I...	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
1. Plan the job I want to perform ahead of time in order to manage time better in situations that I feel stressful.	27	4.63	0.56	Always
2. Pray in situations that I feel stressful.	27	4.48	0.8	Always
3. Create an environment to cope with my stress in situations that I feel stressful.	27	4.37	0.84	Always
4. Positively talk with myself (I look at things from a positive side).	27	4.15	0.91	Often
5. Spare time for my hobbies in situations that feel stressful.	27	4.04	0.85	Often
6. Share the situation causing stress with people I trust in order to cope with my stress.	27	3.89	1.19	Often
7. Spend time with my beloved ones in situations that I feel stressful.	27	3.85	1.17	Often
OVER-ALL MEAN	27	4.20	0.20	Often

The table presents that *I plan the job I want to perform ahead of time to manage time better in a situation that I feel stressful as Always*. This result means that the school head practiced stress management *all the time*. This outcome implies that school heads are already aware that working ahead of time would help lessen stress due to deadlines and records it may give once not on time submitted a report.

This stipulates the findings of Holman et al. (2018) and Hassard et al. (2017), that making blue print s for the task is part of the strategic planning process and includes being clear about goals and outcomes to create plans to achieve them. The disposal as well as any roadblocks to be prepared for should take into account the resources to the process, minimalized the delays, and the school head as well as the teachers. Working the plan is the execution process. It involves a series of milestones, strategies, and actions to make plans a reality. That varied methods to lessen the worry and promote employee wellness

and job restructuring is at the fingertips of the school heads having a variety of skills and procedures.

On the level of Stress Management Practices of Secondary School Heads in terms of Avoidance and Solitude

. Each school is an independent entity and has its own peculiarity, that this particular organizational culture had existed in the past before the school head came (Cabigao 2019). Organizational culture generally involves the belief that staff can learn what to do and what not to do, including practices, values, and assumptions about their job, in which the organization's core values begin with its leadership, which then translates into a leadership style.

Table 2. Stress Management Practices of Secondary School Heads in terms of Avoidance and Solitude

As a secondary school administrator, I...	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
1. avoid situations reminding things causing a stress	27	3.85	1.03	Often
2. confront with the person causing a stress in order to cope with my stress	27	3.78	0.85	Often
3. do sport in situations that I feel stressful	27	3.52	0.94	Often
4. use relaxation methods (meditation yoga, muscle relaxation, deep breathing exercises)	27	3.37	1.11	Sometimes
5. receive support from experts in order to cope with my stress	27	3.26	1.23	Sometimes
6. keep silent in any problem	27	3.11	1.09	Sometimes
7. go shopping	27	2.70	0.99	Sometimes
OVER-ALL MEAN		3.37	0.11	Sometimes

Secondary school administrators use various coping mechanisms to manage stress. They often avoid situations that remind them of stressful events and confront the source of stress. Physical activity, such as sports, is also a common method. While relaxation techniques and seeking expert support are less common, they are still used sometimes. Keeping silent in the face of a problem and going shopping are the least common coping mechanisms. The overall mean score 3.37 indicates that these methods are used sometimes, suggesting that administrators may not be as effective or consistent in managing stress as they could be.

Table 3. Stress Management Practices of Secondary School Heads in terms of Distraction and Social Interaction

As a secondary school administrator, I...	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
1. wanted to be alone	27	2.52	0.98	Seldom
2. do video calls with loved ones/confidantes	27	2.37	1.21	Seldom
3. drink coffee/alcoholic beverages	27	2.26	1.2	Seldom
4. chat in social media	27	2.11	1.25	Seldom
5. do selfie	27	1.96	1.13	Seldom
6. play cyber games (Candy Crash, Plants and Zombies)	27	1.74	1.09	Never
7. take stress tablets	27	1.56	0.85	Never
OVER-ALL MEAN		2.07	0.13	Seldom

The least used stress management practices, as presented in the table, are play cyber games (Candy Crash, Plants and Zombies; take stress tablets; qualitatively described as Never is post emotions in social media which. This realization means, school heads did not practice and find it as not significant in the exercise of their role.

This result was in line with the thoughts of Chen & Leung, L.(2016), described as lonely, quietly bored were persons playing candy crush, and inspired by the mobile games. Frequent players have had a higher tendency to become addicted as predicted. Isolation and self-control were essential predictors of addiction to mobile social games, while leisure boredom was related to game intensity. Mobile games are played primarily for brief periods, between events, and as a way of combating boredom. Giving credence to the notion of being able to experience mobile game play as a casual activity. Results have shown potentially beneficial effects, including improved mood and well-being, better mental concentration, and focus; this was postulated by DaCosta & Seok 2017.

The result also reinforced Vermeulen et al. (2018) that the introduction of social media gave individuals a feeling of varied emotions. While it provides new possibilities for controlling emotions, little is known about how adolescents use various channels for this purpose. The literature on emotion control and the affordances-of-technologies offered insight by explaining how and how adolescents use different uses. Social media platforms (Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat, Twitter, Tumblr, YouTube, 9Gag, and blogs) for sharing of emotions and how technical, social, and contextual factors affect these practices; It also reveals that on multiple of those platforms, adolescents share sentiments.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

The research findings indicate that secondary school administrators employ a variety of stress management practices, with some being used more frequently than others:

Secondary school administrators often plan their work ahead of time, pray, and create an environment to cope with stress. They also positively talk to themselves and make time for hobbies to manage stress.

Administrators often avoid situations that remind them of stress and confront the source of stress directly. They sometimes use physical activity, relaxation techniques, and seek expert support to cope with stress. Keeping silent and going shopping are less common coping mechanisms.

The least used stress management practices include wanting to be alone, doing video calls, drinking coffee/alcohol, using social media, taking selfies, playing video games, and taking stress tablets.

Recommendations

From the conclusion of the study the following recommendations were crafted. Provide training and resources to school administrators on effective stress management techniques, with a focus on proactive strategies like time management, mindfulness, and work-life balance. Encourage administrators to regularly engage in physical activity, relaxation practices, and seek social support to better manage stress.

Implement organizational policies and practices that help reduce workplace stressors, such as reasonable workloads, clear communication, and opportunities for professional development. Offer counseling and mental health services to school administrators to help them cope with the unique challenges of their role.

Foster a school culture that prioritizes employee well-being and provides avenues for administrators to address workplace stress in a healthy manner.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher declares that there was strict compliance with obtaining informed consent, the respondents were given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, the anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was

strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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